

Datasets archiving in the Zenodo repository and in the UCT Prague Zenodo Community

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Here is a guide on **uploading datasets**, **adding acknowledgements** for grants and services, and **linking your Zenodo DOI** to related papers and repositories for data validation.

Step 0: Prepare Your Data

Before starting the Zenodo deposit process, make sure that your data are well organised and ready to publish. This may include:

- Organizing your data files and documentation with folder structure and naming convention.
- Ensuring that your data are properly labelled and annotated.
- Creating a README file that contains basic information about your dataset, such as authorship, protocols used, software used, folder structure, naming convention, etc.

For further information, you are invited to the supporting materials for the [Data Stewardship course](#) on E-Learning, namely chapters 4 and 7.

Step 1: Create and/or Verify Your ORCID Profile

An ORCID iD is a unique identifier that distinguishes you from other researchers. This way, you can have all the information from your publications in one place everyone can see and trust. Zenodo encourages adding your ORCID ID to your profile. If you don't have one, you can create it at <https://orcid.org/register>.

Step 2: Access the Zenodo Deposit Page

If you don't have a Zenodo account yet, you can create one using your ORCID or you can create a separate Zenodo account on the homepage. With your account, go to the deposit site at: <https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=uct-prague>

Step 3: Upload Files

- **Upload Files:** Upload your data files, documentation, and any related files (up to 50 GB, up to 100 files). It is customary to upload folder structures in .zip files. If you are using versioning applications (like git or GitHub), the applications will probably suggest this approach or do it for you.

Step 4: Fill in the Basic Information

- **Resource type:** Choose a resource type from the list (e.g. dataset, software, model, presentation, etc).
- **Title:** Provide a brief and informative title for your dataset.
- **Authors/Creators:** Make sure to include your name and ORCID iD. Multiple authors are allowed. You can also specify contributors so that you don't leave out anyone who contributed to the data.
- **Description:** Write a detailed description of your dataset, including context, purpose, and any relevant information.
- **License:** Choose an appropriate license for your dataset to specify how others can use it. Zenodo offers several license options, e.g. [Creative Commons](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/) licences.
- **Keywords:** Add relevant keywords to help others discover your dataset.

NOTE: Do not forget that Czech Copyright law states:

- Copyright in a work arises at the moment the work is expressed in any objectively perceptible form.
- The author has the right to claim authorship, including the right to decide whether and how authorship should be indicated during the publication and subsequent use of the work if the indication of authorship is customary in such use.
- The author cannot waive personal rights.

Step 5: Set the Deposit Options

- **Publication Date:** Choose the publication date, which can be the current date or a specific date relevant to your dataset.

- **Access Restrictions:** Choose whether your dataset should be open access or restricted in any way. Follow ethical and legal considerations when setting access restrictions.

Step 6: Provide Metadata and Additional Information

- **Version:** If applicable, specify the version of your dataset.
- **Related Works:** You can link to related papers or software in this section.
- **Funding:** Acknowledge the grants and funding sources that supported your research. Include this information in the dataset description and/or README file.
- **References:** Provide relevant literature references, preferably using DOI.
- **Communities:** Select the UCT Prague Zenodo Community (top of the page).
- **Concepts:** Add concepts or terms related to your dataset.
- **DOI:** Zenodo will automatically generate a DOI for your dataset.
- **Related works:** Add any related works as papers, other published data, software, images, etc.

Step 7: Files and Versions

- If you have multiple versions of your dataset, you can manage them here and provide a brief description of the changes.

The screenshot displays the Zenodo dataset upload interface. Key sections include:

- Files:** A table showing the upload progress of 'DummyDataset_2024-01-23.txt' (13 bytes, 100% progress).
- Files Information:** A section highlighted with a yellow border containing metadata fields:
 - Digital Object Identifier:** 10.5281/zenodo.10890096
 - Resource type:** Dataset
 - Title:** Dummy dataset
 - Publication date:** 2024-01-23
 - Creators:** Novak, Jan (University of Chemistry and Technology)
 - Description:** This is a dummy dataset only to showcase the process of uploading to Zenodo. This dataset was created between 22.01.2024 and 23.01.2024 in Prague and contains one text file.
 - License:** Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike 4.0 International
 - Contributors:** Novak, Jan (University of Chemistry and Technology)
 - Keywords and subjects:** dataset, test, test
 - Languages:** English
 - Date:** 2024-01-23/2024-01-23
- Recommended Information:** A section containing 'Contributors' and 'Keywords and subjects'.

Step 8: Review and Publish

Check all the information you have entered and make sure it is correct. You can save the proposal and preview the submission first to see if there are any outstanding issues, such as an invalid ORCID. Once you are satisfied, click the "Publish" button. **Be aware that once the files are published, addition, modification, or removal are no longer possible.**

The screenshot shows the Zenodo upload interface. The top navigation bar includes the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. Below the navigation bar, there is a section for selecting a community. The main content area is divided into two panels: 'Files' and 'Basic information'. The 'Files' panel shows a table with one file: 'DummyDataSet_2024-01-23.txt' (13 bytes, 100% progress). Below the table is a 'Drag and drop files' area with an 'Upload files' button. The 'Basic information' panel is partially visible. A yellow box highlights the 'Draft' stage controls, including 'Save draft', 'Preview', and 'Publish' buttons. Below these are the 'Visibility' settings, which are set to 'Public' (The record and files are publicly accessible.). There is also an 'Options' section with an 'Apply an embargo' button and a 'Delete' button at the bottom.

Step 9: After Publication

- Zenodo will provide you with a DOI for your dataset, which you can use to cite it in your papers and share with others.
- You can add supporting and supplementary information to your dataset information or upload new versions at any time.

Step 10: Share and Promote Your Dataset

Share your published dataset with colleagues, peers, and the research community. Promote it through social media, your academic network, and other relevant platforms.

By following these steps, you can publish your data on Zenodo under the UCT Prague Zenodo Community, provide acknowledgements for grants and services, and link the DOI of your Zenodo dataset to related documents and repositories for data validation and proper attribution.